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Conflicting Conceptualisations of Europeanisation

Greece Country Report

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List of abbreviations

ANEL: Independent Greeks

DIMAR: Democratic Left

EC: European Commission

ECB: European Central Bank

EMU: European Monetary Union

EU: European Union

GD: Golden Dawn

IMF: International Monetary Fund

KKE: Greek Communist Party

LAOS: Popular Orthodox Rally

ND: New Democracy

NGOs: Non-Governmental Organisations

PASOK: Panhellenic Socialist Movement

RIC: Reception and Identification Centre

SYRIZA: Coalition of Radical Left

UNHCR: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

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About the project

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project that aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of 14 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden. The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the European Union (EU), its member states and third countries.

RESPOND will study migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanisation. Each thematic field reflects a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and is designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impact and the responses given by affected actors.

In order to better approach these themes, we divided our research into work packages (WPs). The present report is concerned with the findings related to WP5, which focuses specifically on refugee integration.

Abstract

This report is part of the sixth work package of RESPOND (“Multilevel governance of mass migration in Europe and beyond”) and focuses on the question of Europeanisation. Europeanisation refers to the effect of a normative idea of “Europe” on the policies, politics and practices of domestic actors. The main goal of this report is to examine how conflicting elite discourses of Europeanisation have emerged in the context of increasing migration in the period 2011-2019 in Greece. It aims to capture conflicting Europeanisation in the domestic context; to assess the impact of post-2011 migration on political claim-making about Europe; to develop a perspective on the role of the media in domestic audience-making and to understand how the above situations impact on RESPOND’s stakeholders. It does so through a research methodology that combined diverse methods and data from three sources: political speeches, newspaper articles related to the speeches and a survey addressed to the project’s meso-level stakeholders.

In Greece, the political and social context of the period in question is determined by both the multi-dimensional socioeconomic recession and the increase in refugee arrivals. The financial crisis, the so-called “refugee crisis”, the migration phenomenon in general, as well as their effects emerge as catalysts for an important shift in discourses by politicising questions of Europeanisation. The role of the majority of the media in Greece during the investigated period was – explicitly or implicitly – the reproduction of the different “crises” that characterized the circumstances in the country. As regards the financial crisis and its implications, the majority of mainstream politicians’ and media narratives repeatedly constructed the dilemma of anti-Europe versus pro-Europe while, with respect to the refugee “crisis”, the majority of mainstream politicians’ and media narratives included – among others – the securitization of migration; the necessity of burden and responsibility sharing and “solidarity” among EU member states, and narratives on the “Europeanisation” and “nationalisation” of border security policies. Furthermore, counter-discourses of solidarity with refugees from the part of significant social movements emerged, yet existed in parallel with increased racism and racist violence. Until today, after the 2019 electoral win of the conservative right-wing New Democracy, questions of Europeanisation emerge from a wide range of actors, closely related to migration and refugee issues, resulting in a polarisation of the relevant discourses in Greek society.

Introduction

This report is part of the sixth work package of RESPOND (“Multilevel governance of mass migration in Europe and beyond”) and focuses on issues of Europeanisation. Europeanisation refers to the effect of a normative idea of “Europe” on the policies, politics and practices of domestic actors. Conventionally, this has referred to how the EU impacts on peripheral European states, whether through economic “catch up”, the insertion of established EU practices into domestic policy, or the cultural effect of belonging to advanced transnational systems. Nevertheless, it has been argued that the European Union, through its grid of policies, practices and discourses, has moved away from the idea of a single, shared liberal-democratic ideal. The financial crisis, the so-called “refugee crisis”, the migration issue in general, as well as the effects of all the aforementioned emerge as catalysts for the shift in relevant discourses in the Greek context. Yet, crucial power geometries and inequalities pre-existed among European member states, even before these crises. In this context, “Europeanisation” is currently negotiated, while (institutional and non-institutional) racism is widely expanding, framing Europe as a white, Christian continent defending its borders against the threats of “the strangers” fleeing war and poverty.

The main goal of this report is to examine how conflicting elite discourses of Europeanisation have emerged in the context of increasing migration in the period 2011-2019 in Greece. It aims to capture conflicting Europeanisation in the domestic context; to assess the impact of post-2011 migration on political claim-making about Europe; to develop a perspective on the role of the media in domestic audience-making; and to understand how the above impact on RESPOND’s stakeholders. It does so by investigating how these ideas and claims are constructed by political actors, interpreted through the mass media and deliberated by the project’s stakeholders.

In Greece, the political and social context of the period in question is determined by both the multi-dimensional socioeconomic recession and the increase in refugee arrivals and their forced (or not) stay in the country. The beginning of the last decade in Greece was characterized by discourses insisting on the threats of “illegal migration”. The deepening of the socio-economic inequalities paved the way for the cultivation of racism as well as the rise of extreme right-wing populist and nationalist parties. The refugees’ arrivals in 2015 coincided with the electoral win of SYRIZA, which changed the focus of discourses from “illegal migration” to “refugee/humanitarian crisis”. Until today, after the 2019 electoral win of the conservative right-wing New Democracy, questions of Europeanisation emerge from a wide range of actors, closely related to migration and refugee issues, strengthening the polarisation of the relevant discourses in Greek society.

The report is structured in six sections that discuss and analyse: the developments of the party-political structure; the media structure; the events impacting on asylum/migration discourse since 2011, selected politicians’ speeches during the investigated period, the circulation of narratives of the above speeches in the mainstream media, and the relevant responses of RESPOND’s stakeholders. The report concludes with specific insights emerging from the analysis.

Methodology and Sources

The research methodology used in this report combines diverse methods and data from three distinct sources: political speeches, media articles related to the speeches, and interviews with civil society organisations active in migration field. In summary, the research design is as follows.

- Identifying political claims (slogans, sayings, metaphors). The data came from 10 speeches by major political actors (leading or serving in government, or official opposition leaders) containing explicit references to the future of the EU and developments in migration. Analytical tables were used to generate narrative categories on diverging courses of Europeanisation in relation to immigration. For each politician's speech, a coding system has been used in this report. This coding includes the year of the speech and the name of the politician (for example: (GR1-2012-Papoutsis)). A relevant data base including the sources that were used is provided in the Annex.

- Media audience-making on Europeanisation. This data came from newspaper articles commenting on the 10 speeches, focusing on the construction of discourses and themes, particularly insofar as they construct audiences. Three major groups of Greek newspapers were defined, belonging to the following categories: Conservative, Liberal and Centre-left. "Kathimerini" and "Enikos.gr" were included in the conservative group of newspapers; "To Vima", "Ta Nea", "Naftemporiki" in the liberal group; and "Eleftherotypia", "H Efimerida ton Sintakton" and "H Avgi" were included in the centre-left group. It should be mentioned that, in some cases, there were no articles from specific political media groups commenting on the 10 politicians' speeches. In such cases, the choice of specific media not to reproduce specific politicians' speeches is itself a key finding. For each media article analysed, the coding – apart from the parts that refer to the political speeches – also includes the code of the position of the respective media in the political spectrum (for example: (GR1-2012-Papoutsis-LIB)). The abbreviation "CONS" refers to the group of conservative media, "LIB" to the liberal, and "CELEF" to the centre-left. A relevant database, including the sources that were used, is provided in the Annex.

- Stakeholder responses to Europeanisation. Stakeholders have been defined as actors with a meaningful institutionalized practice (at social/economic or political level) in relation to migration and asylum. Data were drawn from a survey that was addressed to civil society active in migration field. The survey provided – among others – three contrasting quotations of politicians' speeches in relation to a similar issue. It focused on how stakeholders respond to the abovementioned political and media discourses, and the ways in which these discourses affect their work in the field. The survey was addressed to 15 stakeholders, of which five responded.

1. Party-Political Structure: History and Developments since 2011

In Greece, the political and social context of the period in question is determined by the multi-dimensional (economic, social, political) crisis, the increase in refugee arrivals and the forced stay of many of them in the country, due to specific border and asylum policies applied since 2016 (such as the closure of the “Western Balkan Corridor”, the EU-Turkey Statement and the Hotspot Approach).

Since its entry into the Eurozone, despite the fact that it had to compete with countries with stronger economies, Greece considered that merely its participation in the currency union would bring positive economic effects (Tassis, 2015). Despite the fact that during the early 2000s Greece experienced some successes such as an economic growth or the hosting of the Olympic Games, substantial social deficits as well as high unemployment rates existed in parallel (Tassis, 2015). As a result, in 2009 the global economic crisis hit the Greek economy and had enormous social and political consequences for Greek society. Shrinking of the public sector, soaring unemployment rates, increased impoverishment, and emigration were some of the effects of the crisis and the austerity measures on the population of the country (Petraçou et al., 2018). Since then, Greece has witnessed the rise of a massive anti-austerity social movement. 2011 in particular saw the emergence of the movement of the “*indignados*” / the “squares” in large Greek cities, following similar developments in other Southern European countries.

The crisis not only led to the deepening of socio-economic inequalities among the population, but also had an impact on the party-political structure of Greece. The investigated period (2011-2019) was characterized by massive social discontent against the economic situation and by successive changes of governments. In 2009, approximately six months before the economic bailout of Greece, national elections were called by the Prime Minister of the conservative right-wing “New Democracy” (ND) Costas Karamanlis, and the “Panhellenic Socialist Movement” (PASOK) returned to power. From the beginning of 2010, Greece adopted a bailout strategy engineered by the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the European Union (EU) and the European Central Bank (ECB), known as “Troika”. Prime Minister George Papandreou requested a bailout for Greece, and the EU, the ECB, and the IMF responded to this call. The first memorandum was signed, and the first bailout package was agreed by the Eurozone leaders and IMF. During 2010, austerity measures were voted by the Greek parliament amid strikes, demonstrations, and the “squares” movement took place in large Greek cities, mainly 2011-2012. Papandreou resigned under this pressure in November 2011 and Lucas Papademos, former head of the Bank of Greece and not elected, became the new Prime Minister of a three-party coalition government consisting of the PASOK, ND and the extreme right-wing populist “Popular Orthodox Rally” (LAOS).

The adoption of the first bailout package and the so-called Memorandum resulted in changes in the electorate system from one party-governments to coalition ones, while public attention and the media focused on the economic crisis and the ability of political parties to negotiate reforms with “Troika”. The second bailout and set of austerity measures adopted by the coalition government in June 2011 led to the decomposition of PASOK and ND, the latter changing its position and supporting a pro-bailout agreement. Papademos resigned in April 2012 after two rounds of elections. ND won and formed a coalition government with PASOK and “Democratic Left” (DIMAR) with Prime Minister Antonis Samaras, leader of New

Democracy. Furthermore, in the 2012 national elections, the neo-Nazi organization “Golden Dawn” (GD) entered the Parliament, where it held the third position from 2015 until 2019. In December 2014, Greek Parliament failed to approve the government's candidate for President of the Republic: Stavros Dimas replaced retiring President Karolos Papoulias, and national elections were scheduled for January 2015. SYRIZA (the Coalition of the Radical Left) won the elections with great hopes of rejecting the austerity imposed by the “Troika” and formed government with “Independent Greeks” (ANEL) a conservative, extreme right-wing populist party.

Greece joined the European Union in 1981 in order to modernize its economy and society, stabilize the democratic regime and acquire allies in its relations with Turkey. In general, Greek governments supported the idea and process of European integration and EU enlargement. Until the Eurozone crisis and concomitant Greek financial crisis, most political parties in the Greek parliament – except for the Communist Party (KKE) and the Popular Orthodox Rally (LAOS) – and the public opinion were in favour of the EU and European integration. However, political debate on the benefits of bailout and the contestation of austerity measures resulted in intense Europeanisation (Altiparmakis, 2019). As Chrysosgelos pointed out “austerity brought about a re-politicisation of a whole range of state-society relations that, under the influence of EU membership, had entailed (or intended) the insulation of Greek political and administrative elites” (2017: 9).

Figure 1. Perceptions about European Union in Greece from 2000-2020.¹

Katsanidou and Otjes argued that “there was a significant correlation between pro-/anti-EU and economic positions for the parties and the pro-/anti-bail-out self-placement for the voters” (2016: 19), while a cultural dimension depends on the “left-right dimension that centred on cultural issues from the cluster immigration– integration–security–defence” (2016: 19).

In this context, Golden Dawn (Chrissi Avgi) – which “...capitalised on its electoral success in the 2010 municipal election in the city of Athens ... by benefiting from the favourable ‘anti-

¹ Source: Eurobarometer, 2020. Public Opinion, Greece [online] Available at: <https://bit.ly/3dVjnGd> [Accessed 20 October 2020].

immigrant' agenda that ND and PASOK had set during the campaign" [of 2012 elections] ...and was the most anti-systemic and anti-parliamentarian party – made its stance clear in both prevailing issues: it argued for the punishment of the parties and politicians who supported the bailout programmes and expressed extreme anti-bailout positions" (Dinas and Rori, 2013: 277). Immigration had already become part of the political agenda by the ND and PASOK in the 2012 elections campaign. Samara's promises in the election campaign in 2012 were, firstly, to "deport immediately all illegal migrants", and, secondly, to renegotiate the Memoranda austerity agreements (Markontonatou, 2016). Golden Dawn, ANEL and LAOS were all positioned against immigration while SYRIZA, DIMAR and KKE advocated a multicultural approach to immigration (Katsanidou and Otjes, 2016). After his party's defeat in elections in January 2015, Samaras stated "I hand over a country that is part of the EU and the Eurozone. For the good of this country, I hope the next government will maintain what we saved" (Euronews, 2015).

As Vasilopoulou argued, "PASOK and New Democracy maintained their pro-EU positions... justified their pro-EU attitudes in terms of meeting the country's economic interests through EU participation. The Ecologist Greens, DIMAR, and The River, which were situated on the Europhile end of the spectrum. KKE continued to call for Greece's withdrawal from the EU and the unilateral suspension of the country's debt payments...SYRIZA forwarded a 'radical criticism' of the EU and offered its alternative vision of a socialist Europe defined as 'a Europe of employment, rights, solidarity, democracy, peace, progressive development, gender equality, without racism or homophobia; a Europe that guarantees equality among its peoples'" (2018: 13).

During this period, narratives regarding the relation between Greece and the EU became highly politicised. SYRIZA came to power due to its promises to confront the "Troika", to secure an exit from the Greek debt crisis, and to end austerity without, however, taking the country out of the European Monetary Union (EMU). At the same time, discussions on a possible and probably desirable "Grexit" increased among part of the SYRIZA party, other parties and organizations of the radical left, and some intellectuals. These discourses insisted on an alternative policy including writing off debt, nationalizing banks, redistributing income and wealth through tax reform, raising the minimum wage, restoring labour regulation, boosting public investment, and reintroducing the national currency for the implementation of the above (Lapavitsas, 2015).

Nevertheless, SYRIZA's coalition government had already signed the agreement of February 2015 for a new loan for Greece. After five months of negotiations with the EU in early 2015 amid imposed capital controls, SYRIZA called for a national referendum in which the Greek people had to answer "yes" or "no" to the deal offered by "Troika". This referendum of July 2015 could have been a point of rupture with the EU, and many media and political actors presented it this way by cultivating fears of exiting the EU. 62 percent voted "no" in the referendum; however, the Greek Parliament approved the measures of the "Troika" by signing the third bailout agreement in August 2015. Due to the former campaign of SYRIZA against austerity packages and the split between SYRIZA MPs and the party, Prime Minister Alexis Tsipras called elections in September 2015 which resulted in the victory of SYRIZA and its forming, once again, a coalition government with ANEL. Since then, austerity measures have been continuously applied.

If the financial crisis was the context in which the narratives on the relationship between the European Union and Greece increased, especially through discussions of economic

dependency, the uneven politico-economic relationship among EU member states, the issue of Grexit, and the so-called “refugee crisis” of 2015-16 also rekindled this rhetoric. As analysed in the third section of this report, the closure of the borders of many EU countries during early 2016 turned Greece into a country where significant numbers² of asylum seekers were forced to stay. The EU-Turkey Statement of March 2016 not only led to the inhuman treatment of refugees but also placed a huge burden on Greece as regards migration management. Discussions on the need for burden-sharing and solidarity between EU member states, as well as on the failure of the Dublin Regulation, constituted common narratives among most of the country’s governing political parties since the sharp rise in the number of refugee arrivals.

It should be also mentioned that the circumstances of the examined period, the increased socio-economic inequalities in the population, and the dominant xenophobic and racist narratives and policies – especially since 2010 – created a fertile ground for the rise of extreme right-wing populist parties such as “Independent Greeks” (ANEL) and “Popular Orthodox Rally” (LAOS). ANEL was founded in 2012, entered Parliament during the financial crisis and participated in the SYRIZA-led coalition government. LAOS was founded in 2000 and entered Parliament in 2007. LAOS’ participation in the technocratic coalition government of 2011-2012 led to its collapse. The rise of extreme right-wing populism, along with the cultivation of racism and xenophobia by the dominant media and political discourses permitted the rise of “Golden Dawn” (GD), it had its first electoral breakthrough in the Athens City Council in the municipal elections of 2010, and in the 2012³ national elections it entered Parliament, where it held third position from 2015 until 2019. In the 2019 national elections, GD failed to enter Parliament⁴. Even if GD is usually reported as an extreme right-wing populist party, it is a neo-Nazi organization with an agenda dominated by racist, nationalist, and anti-immigrant rhetoric (Papatzani *forthcoming*). The racism that was cultivated back then, as well as racist practices against immigrants and refugees, continue until today, despite GD’s failure to enter Parliament or its ongoing trial.⁵ Counter-discourses of solidarity with migrants and refugees from the part of International Organizations, NGOs and significant social movements also determined the recent period – yet existed in parallel with the increased racism and racist violence.

² From 4,814 asylum applications in 2013, 77,285 asylum applications were recorded in 2019 in Greece. For more information see: Greek Asylum Service (2020) Asylum Service Statistics (from 07.06.2013 to 29.02.2020) [online] Available at: <https://bit.ly/2St5x3Q>.

³ The election results for Golden Dawn in the period 2012-2019 are the following: May 2012: 6.7% and 21 seats out of 300; June 2012: 6.9 (18/300); January 2015: 6.3% (17/300); September 2015: 7% (18/300).

⁴ In July 2019 GD obtained 2.9% and did not manage to enter Parliament since it did not gain the 3% of the country’s votes, required for a party to enter Parliament.

⁵ In September 2013, following the murder of Pavlos Fyssas – also known as Killah P., a Greek musician and rapper – the Greek Police arrested the leadership of Golden Dawn, as well as tens of its party officials and members, who were involved in the criminal activities included in the huge case file. After a long inquest which lasted 9 months, the Court of Appeal decided with irrevocable decree that 69 individuals, including all of Golden Dawn’s Parliamentary Group from the 2012 elections, will stand trial charged with participation in a criminal organisation. For more details see: <https://goldendawnwatch.org/?lang=en>.

2. Media Structure and the Question of Europeanisation

In the recent history of the Greek media, three phases of development are observed: a) in the mid-1980s, when the newspaper market was affected, b) in the late 1980s, with the deregulation of the state broadcasting of two public television channels and four public radio stations, which resulted in the creation of numerous private TV channels and radio stations, and c) in the mid-1990s when the magazine sector expanded and the competition between the emerging electronic media and Greek newspapers increased (Papathanassopoulos, 2001). Generally speaking, during the last decades Greece has undergone a process of broadcasting commercialization, adopting a market-led approach. More specifically, the owners of the main commercial TV stations also owned newspapers, magazines, and radio stations, and were involved in other sectors of the economy (Papathanassopoulos, 2001).

An important development in the recent history of the media in Greece took place in June 2013, when the conservative-led government took state broadcaster ERT off the air and dismissed its 2,600-strong staff as part of a cost-cutting initiative demanded by the country's international creditors. The end of ERT was considered by a large part of opposing political parties as a damage to pluralism in Greek journalism, as ERT – although seen as promoting the government narratives and having a state-appointed board – was the only broadcaster legally obliged to air unbiased news. Its official closure was followed by huge demonstrations, with protesting employees joined by opposition politicians and union leaders. As a countermovement, many journalists continued to hold self-managed broadcasts of “ERT Open” until they were evicted by police forces. “ERT Open” was a nationwide attempt, between 2013 and 2015, to manage and produce media as “commons”. ERT was later replaced with NERIT, a media with a smaller budget and staff base under the control of the government. In 2015, the new SYRIZA coalition government restored ERT, and NERIT ceased broadcasting.

The role of the mainstream media was crucial during the economic crisis in Greece. According to Pleios (2013), media actors supported austerity policies and reproduced the views of the elites mainly in order to survive, as they depended on both the banks and the political elites which implemented austerity policies. It should also be mentioned that, from the beginning of the Greek crisis, the European media presented Greece as an exception within Europe and as largely responsible for Eurozone's crisis. A front-cover image from German magazine “Focus” with the famous statue of Aphrodite of Milos giving the finger to the Greeks “for betraying the Euro family” received worldwide attention and criticism (Mylonas, 2012). Another example was German Chancellor Merkel and former French President Sarkozy repeatedly arguing that Greece is a “special case” (BBC 2012), responsible for its crisis, and that the Eurozone risks being “contaminated” by Greece's economic crisis.

These discourses have been instrumentalised on a permanent basis by Greek politicians and have been reproduced by the Greek mainstream media (Kaitatzi-Whitlock, 2014). Since 2011 the Greek media have been conforming to “Troika” as supporters of the country's affiliation to the “Euro”. Furthermore, they have been reproducing a division of political parties between those who wish to remain in the Eurozone and those who do not (Kaitatzi-Whitlock, 2014).

In general, during the economic crisis in Greece, mainstream Greek newspapers adopted a neoliberal interpretation of the economic crisis as relating to the pathologies of the Greek society (Mylonas, 2014). At the same time, “the elites use crisis as a vehicle in order to occupy the media and, furthermore, influence public opinion regarding the implementation of austerity

policies” (Pleios, 2013, p. 27). The coverage of the economic crisis in Greece by the mainstream media was largely characterized by the aforementioned fact, while their role also extended to defining what “crisis” means, its causes and the possible solutions (Pleios, 2013). In contrast, several smaller newspapers and influential internet media adopted oppositional stances to “Troika”, by projecting “the crisis” as a stage for the implementation of neoliberal austerity policies on Greek economy (Kaitatzi-Whitlock, 2014). “The dichotomy between pro- and anti-memorandum media adherents is observable in all vital conflicts” (Kaitatzi-Whitlock, 2014, p. 37).

Mylonas (2014), in his research on the mainstream conservative media in Greece and the neoliberal articulations of the economic crisis (based on the example of Ekathimerini newspaper), identifies – among others – the following axes around which the anti-political and anti-democratic neoliberal politics unfold: a) the construction of the ‘crisis’ as a problem of specific countries and specific people who ‘lived beyond their means or were corrupted. This was reproduced in the case of Greece as the “problematic infant or a deviant alien in the ‘Eurofamily’” (Mylonas, 2014, p. 310); b) the construction of ‘us’ and ‘them’ while addressing the crisis; c) the construction of a positive Greek identity in need, in order for the Greeks to internalize the norms that (neoliberal) Europe incarnates. “Prolonged austerity appears as essential for a ‘new Greece’ to emerge, that is (economically) dynamic, entrepreneurial and more European” (Mylonas, 2014, p. 313).

For the Greek mainstream media, the arrivals of refugees in 2015-16 were an added opportunity to construct another “crisis”. Since the transformation of Greece into a destination country in the early 1990s, the mainstream media have been constructing immigrants as “illegals” and “dangerous”, reproducing xenophobic and racist discourses. During the early 2010s these discourses increased, following the political programs and narratives of the right-wing conservative government of that period. With the refugee arrivals of 2015-2016, the relevant dominant discourse shifted: “illegal migration” was left behind and was replaced by the term “refugee crisis”, while the formerly used term *lathrometanastes* (“illegal immigrants”) was replaced by the term “refugees”. The images of dead children on the Greek beaches of the North Aegean islands were widely reproduced by the majority of the Greek media. The spontaneous waves of solidarity by Greek people also had an impact on the discourses of the mainstream media, through the reproduction of the massive support that the volunteers provided to refugees.

Nevertheless, this attitude did not last for long. The closure of the “Western Balkan Corridor” and the EU-Turkey Statement of March 2016, which resulted in the forced stay of asylum seekers in Greece, were crucial in yet another turn in the narratives of the mainstream Greek media, as they moved from “humanitarian crisis” to the problem of the “refugee crisis”. The most conservative media focused on the number of refugee arrivals; the xenophobic reactions of local communities; the supposed negative effects of the refugee issue on tourism (especially on the Greek islands); the alleged infectious diseases and epidemics brought by the refugees; or the ‘downgrading’ of areas where accommodation was provided to refugees.

In contrast, a number of “alternative” online media focussed on the rights of refugees and on their personal stories and their hopes and dreams for a better future. They provided information on refugee protection and reception, reproduced the ways in which refugees were treated by the authorities, and the living conditions in the Hotspots and camps. It should be mentioned, however, that an extensive criticism of the choices of the political authorities was missing – especially during the SYRIZA-ANEL coalition government (2015-2019) – even from

the relatively alternative or left media. Criticism of the anti-refugee choices of the government was reinforced especially after the elections of 2019 and the rise of right-wing conservative New Democracy to power.

Overall, the role of the majority of the media in Greece during the investigated period was – explicitly or implicitly – the reproduction of the different “crises” that characterized the circumstances in Greece. The ways in which this construction took place always depended on the political stance of the respective media - yet significant similarities can be observed, ones that create separate and dividing narratives and construct the respective audiences.

3. Events Impacting on Migration Discourse since 2011

Until the 1990s, Greece was mainly an emigration country, sending migrants and refugees worldwide due to the 1944-1949 civil war, the subsequent persecution and marginalization of the Left, and the 1967-1974 dictatorship (Petraçou et al., 2018). From the 1990s onwards, Greece is considered to have transformed into a destination country for migration movements mainly from Eastern European countries and the Balkans, after the dissolution of the USSR. Greek immigration policy back then was characterized by the adoption of strict immigration and naturalization laws and was accompanied by the negative coverage of the migration phenomenon by the mass media. The main focus of the respective policies and narratives until the late 2000s was to combat the irregular arrival of people; strengthen border controls; provide temporary residence and employment permits for the migrant population; as well as implement restrictive and limited asylum policies (Petraçou et al., 2018).

In the early 2010s, the deepening of socio-economic inequalities, the austerity measures and the increased impoverishment of the population during the economic crisis in Greece provided a fertile ground for the construction of “enemies”. “Illegal immigrants” (*lathrometanastes*) were constructed by part of the dominant media and political discourses as the scapegoats of the crisis, responsible for most socio-economic problems (Papatzani, forthcoming). Back then, the focus of migration narratives was on combating “illegal migration”, through the intensification of border controls at the northern Greek borders (Ilias et al., 2019). More specifically, in 2011, Greek political authorities celebrated the adoption of the Integrated Border Management Program for Combating Illegal Immigration, including the construction of the Evros fence at the Greek-Turkish northeast borders. The main targets of this program were “the protection of both the EU and national borders” and the “reduction of illegal migration” (Ministry of Citizen Protection, 2011). Grigoriadis and Dilek (2018) argued that “national-level discourse by political actors reveals that the construction of the fence was linked to the wider EU-level migration and border control practices, as well as to the national-level perception of migration as a security issue” (Grigoriadis and Dilek, 2018, p. 2).

Since 2012, the newly elected coalition government led by conservative right-wing ND strengthened the dominant political narrative in the aforementioned direction. From 2012 until 2014, a dominant political discourse regarding the urban space of the large Greek cities emerged. Although the mainstream discourse of the early 1990s focused on the overall denunciation of the migrant “invasion”, at the beginning of the 2010s it was clearly characterized by anti-immigrant and racist elements (Kalantzopoulou et al., 2011; Koutrolikou and Siatitsa, 2011). This anti-immigrant and racist discourse applied the term “ghetto” to specific central urban areas in Athens; the role of nationalist parties (e.g. the neo-Nazis of Golden Dawn) and practices was also crucial in this. Despite the fact that the discourse focused on the urban centres, it was linked directly to the protection of the Greek borders. Policies of immigrant persecution in the city centre through official “sweep” operations were implemented, such as police operation “Xenios Zeus”, with the declared aim of combating “illegal migration and crime” (Papakonstantis, 2012). This policy, along with the transfer and detention of the “illegal” immigrants in closed centres in the mainland, was also part of the Integrated Border Management Program for Combating Illegal Immigration.

Additionally, politically conservative and racist discourses have always been reproduced by political parties, official institutions and media actors alike, even before the beginning of the so-called refugee crisis. Extreme right-wing populist parties emerged and strengthened during the economic crisis, creating a fertile ground for the emergence and electoral win of neo-Nazi

organisation Golden Dawn. Practices of racist violence in local contexts were strengthened since then (Kandylis and Kavoulakos, 2011) and exist until today, even after the electoral defeat of GD in the recent 2019 national elections.

Migration narratives were shaped by the arrival of hundreds of thousands of migrants and refugees fleeing war, poverty, and political instability in the Middle East, Africa, and elsewhere since 2015. After 2015, both refugee arrivals in Greece and the change of government (SYRIZA and ANEL coalition government from 2015 until 2019) constituted significant factors for the transformation of the dominant political discourse. During this turn, the term “illegal migration” was left behind and replaced by the terms “humanitarian crisis” and “refugee crisis” in the dominant discourse of the Greek government and of a wide range of other actors (including International Organizations, the EU, NGOs, and scholars). Furthermore, the coalition government started to use the term “border management” instead of previously used terms “border protection” or “border control” (Ilias et al., 2019).

Since 2015, international and local NGOs, social movements, solidarity initiatives, and activists have provided their services to respond to refugee reception. The images of dead children on the Greek beaches of the North Aegean islands created strong sentiments of empathy towards the newcomers passing through the country, and a considerable part of Greek society responded spontaneously and engaged in practices of solidarity (such as donations of goods or money). Organized efforts and initiatives of solidarity also spread across the country.

Nevertheless, the closure of the “Western Balkan Corridor” and the EU-Turkey Statement of March 2016 resulted in the forced stay of a considerable number of people in inadequate and precarious conditions in overcrowded “Hotspots” on the North Aegean islands and on camps in mainland Greece. These developments were treated differently in dominant narratives and also had an impact on peoples’ perceptions and on the reduction of the massive wave of solidarity of 2015-2016, once again giving space to xenophobic discourses. Until today, in parallel with lasting solidarity (especially through organized political initiatives), racist attitudes, prejudice, and even racist violence against refugees and asylum seekers still prevail in different contexts all over the country, in urban neighbourhoods, peri-urban areas where mainland camps are located, as well as on the islands where RICs are established (RVRN, 2018).

More recently, a new law on International Protection (Law 4636/2019) was adopted by the 2019 elected right-wing conservative government of ND, followed by a number of amendments (such as the Law 4686/2020). The adopted legislation curtailed rights of asylum seekers leading to even more hurdles to access the asylum procedure, mass rejections and less protection for vulnerable groups. Furthermore, the government announcements on the establishment of “closed centres” on the islands triggered large protests by the local communities who oppose them, with the participation of different political groups: from progressive ones demanding the decongestion of the Hotspots, to the far-right and racist groups that were strengthened through the xenophobic discourses cultivated by the dominant government discourse of the recent period. There have also been negative attitudes of local communities towards the (I)NGO personnel, reflecting the shifts that have occurred in the political scene.

4. Political Speeches: Analytical Tables

During the period in question, discourses of Europeanisation have been closely linked to the so-called “refugee crisis”. The impact of refugee flows on the character of the EU was filtered through different approaches and narratives. In most of them, political actors cultivate an explicit fear of migration. They insist on terms such as “illegal migration” and the threat it represents for European democracies, as Antonis Samaras, leader of New Democracy, stated in 2017: *“We must realize that European democracies in the Mediterranean are in danger of being swept away by a “tsunami” of uncontrolled immigration!”* (GR8-2017-Samaras). The impact of migration on the nation state was also discussed, as well as on the so called “western culture” as pointed out by Nikos Toskas, Deputy Minister of Citizen Protection during the SYRIZA-ANEL government in 2017.

In general, migration is widely and explicitly discussed as a **security issue** by centre-right and right-wing parties, and more implicitly by the SYRIZA party. The latter is mostly related to the implementation of strict border and asylum policies by the SYRIZA-ANEL coalition government. Its recognition of the serious problems of the Greek protection and reception system ran in parallel with its support towards the implementation of the EU-Turkey Statement as a *“top priority to eliminate primary flows”* (GR9-2018-Tsipras). Despite the acknowledgement by SYRIZA that *“the fences and the walls cannot stop the flows of the forced moving populations [...]”, “this does not mean that Europe can and must pursue a policy of “open” or “fluid” borders”* (GR7-2017-Toskas). Instead, proposals made by Prime Minister Alexis Tsipras included the strengthening of security mechanisms and policies as regards border management and control.

The aforementioned discourses in the speeches of politicians are also closely related to the **rise of racism**, especially in Greece. With regards to New Democracy, the increase of racism and the nationalist rhetoric is discussed as a consequence of *“crossing borders as one pleases”* (GR2-2013-Dendias).

One of the important discourses during the investigated period is **the need for burden and responsibility-sharing among EU member states**. Greece’s geographical position constitutes the key argument regarding the uneven migration burdens placed on the country, both in terms of refugee arrivals through its borders and their stay in the country, including their asylum applications. As Christos Papoutsis (member of PASOK government, Minister of Citizen Protection) mentioned in 2011 when border controls were at the centre of the migration policy, *“in fact, we brought Europe to its external borders, highlighted the European dimension of the problem by shedding light on all its complex aspects”* (GR1-2012-Papoutsis). Despite the change of government, a similar discourse was also articulated by Vangelis Meimarakis (chairperson of the Hellenic Parliament) who insisted on *“common (EU) responsibility”*: *“Greece has a disproportionately heavy burden in managing illegal migratory flows whose ultimate destination is central and northern Europe”* (GR3-2014-Meimerakis).

Criticism of the Dublin Regulation was also on the rise during that period, as Nikos Dendias of ND (Minister of Public Order during 2013) argued: *“Greece has, for the first time with this government, changed its policy. It did not agree with this regulation. It did not agree to the criterion of the first country of entry”* (GR2-2013-Dendias). Until recently, the SYRIZA-ANEL coalition government insisted on the need for a new relevant regulation that would be able to redistribute migration burdens more effectively: *“The third dimension of our migration policy is the sharing of responsibility and burden as well as solidarity [...] a redistribution*

process based on a new Dublin [...] The EU focuses only on border protection and not on the other dimensions of migration policy” (GR10-2018-Vitsas).

Closely related to the aforementioned narratives, **the need for solidarity between EU member states** also emerges, especially in the fields of asylum, border and migration management. These issues were also brought forward by both leading governments during the examined period (conservative right-wing ND and SYRIZA-ANEL government). The need for solidarity was highlighted by Vangelis Meimarakis: *“the management of uncontrolled immigration must be based on the principles of solidarity, co-responsibility and respect for fundamental rights and human dignity”* (GR3-2014-Meimerakis) but also by SYRIZA, as Prime Minister Alexis Tsipras stated during 2018, following an informal EU leaders mini-summit on asylum and migration in Brussels: *“Europe must strive for a policy of shared responsibility, solidarity and mutual support and not allow the countries that received migration flows to shoulder the burden alone”* (GR9-2018-Tsipras). As such, the notion of “solidarity” between EU member states is a common issue for both the SYRIZA-ANEL coalition and previous governments, while the former insists on the need for *“true solidarity”*. The principle of *“true solidarity”* between EU member states, the need for mutual support and burden-sharing within the EU (and not only their undertaking by reception countries such as Greece) has been continuously highlighted. According to Nikos Toskas (Minister of Citizen Protection), the main problems hindering the management of the refugee crisis by the EU were the low level of solidarity between member states and the uneven pressures placed on their shoulders, among others. The SYRIZA government also called for more EU solidarity as a way to overcome the “refugee crisis”. Moreover, criticism emerged against the “nationalisation” of border control (GR7-2017-Toskas).

Although the prevailing terminology shifted during SYRIZA’s term in office from “illegal migrants” to “deserving refugees”, the **distinction between migrants and refugees** was never abandoned. The term “illegal migrants”, that was the norm in the discourse of right-wing politicians and media actors before 2015, was not chosen by chance; it was a political choice as, according to the Public Order Minister Nikos Dendias of ND, “illegal immigration” was the most appropriate notion. As he stated

We will neither hide the terms nor try to embellish them. And we also demand the continued use of the term 'illegal' as opposed to 'irregular' in the European political vocabulary. For us this is absolutely clear. The violation of the Greek and European borders is a criminal offense according to Greek law and specifically Law 3386/2005 [...] European borders must be protected from people not entitled to international protection (GR2-2013-Dendias).

In this context, a clear distinction was made in dominant political discourses between “legal” immigrants and refugees, deserving international protection, and “illegals”, towards whom *“we will not show sympathy when protecting our national sovereignty and our borders. It is our right”* (GR2-2013-Dendias). These distinctions have been reproduced by political actors of ND from 2015 until today:

The real refugees still arriving are 20% of the total number, or less [...] The refugees are people who come from war zones, from dissolved states, from civil wars or from tyrannical regimes. We cannot and should not turn our back on them. [...] The economic migrants come to Europe looking for "opportunities", but they do not accept any of the responsibilities of an open democracy. They usually engage in all kinds of smuggling: drugs, trafficking, and even "jihad". We cannot allow this! The freedom and openness of our societies also entail responsibilities! [...] Refugees can expect regular asylum and relocation to other

European states, illegal immigrants must be controlled and kept in guarded areas pending their repatriation (GR8-2017-Samaras)

Opposing narratives emerged within SYRIZA as regards this distinction and the characterization of migrants and refugees as follows. “When they need migrants as cheap labour, they’re fine with it. In cases of social protest, the migrant becomes the enemy [...] For the elite of a number of countries, the enemy is the refugee, the migrant” (GR10-2018-Vitsas).

Following the narratives on the need for burden-sharing between EU member states, a rhetoric on border security policies emerged consisting of two opposite but mostly complementary discussions: narratives on the **“Europeanisation” of border security policies**; and narratives on the **“Nationalisation” of border security policies**. All governments and political actors of the investigated period insisted on the need for a European response to Greek border management, calling the EU to assist Greece, as “the pressures on the eastern borders are not indifferent to any member state of the European family” (GR3-2014-Meimerakis). Alexis Tsipras, for example, asked in 2018 for the replacement of the EU border agency Frontex with a powerful European border and coast guard. The notion of European border management “beyond the EU borders”, in the countries of origin, also emerged.

At the same time, the need for national initiatives on border management beyond EU decisions and common management was also voiced. In 2012, during the construction of the Evros Fence and due to the disagreement of the EU, Christos Papoutsis, Minister of Citizen Protection, stated that Greece should be able to make its own decisions regarding border control, that “Europe should stop behaving hypocritically regarding the tackling of illegal immigration” and that “it would be better for the European Commission to remain within its remit and respect the legal order of the European Union” (GR1-2012-Papoutsis). Relevant speeches were made by political actors of ND as regards the right of Greece “to protect its national sovereignty and its borders” (GR2-2013-Dendias). Since 2015, the debate on border management and migration control has also influenced discourses on national sovereignty. Following the same line of argumentation, SYRIZA politicians also engaged with similar narratives. They moved from asking for a “fluid” border policy from the part of Europe to stating that “if the Union fails to effectively safeguard the external borders and ensure a fair distribution of burdens among member states, the risk of a more comprehensive nationalisation of policies will become a reality” (GR7-2017-Toskas).

5. Dissemination of Narratives in the Mainstream Media

For the purposes of this report, the dissemination of the political speeches was investigated in three major political groups of Greek newspapers belonging to the following categories: Conservative, Liberal and Centre-Left. In some cases, certain media chose not to reproduce specific politicians' speeches, usually from the opposite side of the political spectrum. This is an interesting fact, as it reveals the choices of the media not only in relation to the reproduction (or not) of specific political positions but also to the construction of their audiences.

In most cases, the **conservative media** reproduced almost all discourses of the more conservative or right-wing politicians. In their discourse and audience-making, migration is presented as a security issue, and the distinction between refugees and “illegal immigrants” (as reproduced by politicians' speeches) is maintained and strengthened. A contradiction also emerges as regards Europe when studying the dissemination of narratives in the conservative media. On the one hand, the conservative media reproduce a discourse according to which “a stronger Europe is needed”, in opposition to Euroscepticism and anti-European voices emerging in the public discourse. Euroscepticism is described as a problem that must be overcome, and this can be attained only if Europe is treated “not as a necessary evil but as a space that can provide solutions if we coordinate and discuss more, identify the issues that concern us and answer with the solutions that we must have” (GR3-2014-Meimerakis-CONS). On the other hand, a division of the audience emerges, whereby the dividing line between people (and between parts of the audience) is that of Europeans and anti-Europeans and not of ideologies such as socialism, liberalism or other. At the same time, the need for burden and responsibility-sharing between EU member states has been reproduced in the conservative media, as well as in the liberal and centre-left media as described below. It seems that the narrative on burden-sharing is common among different politicians and media actors in Greece, regardless of political positions.

The **liberal media** analysed insisted mainly on reproducing the speeches of politicians discussing the importance of the EU and, more specifically, of its fundamental values and the principles on which it is built (GR5-2016-Kotzias-LIB). The call for an EU of freedom, democracy, development and prosperity is highlighted, as well as for a Europe with more participation, solidarity, and a stronger social state (GR3-2014-Meimerakis-CONS). This must be combined with policies and practices for secure borders (GR8-2017-Samaras-LIB). Emphasis is placed on “European values” and the need for the protection of national sovereignty and borders, despite the increased number of refugee deaths at the Greek borders (GR2-2013-Dendias-LIB). The growth of populism across Europe is also a narrative that is reproduced based on the politicians' discourses, as a result of the European Union's inability to propose clear solutions for refugee management and the emergence of nationalist and xenophobic attitudes (GR7-2017-Toskas-LIB).

The **centre-left media** analysed were more critical of the role of the EU as regards refugee issues – yet the mainstream centre-left media did not reproduce a clear anti-European stance. Instead, there is a stressing of the need for “solidarity” among member states and for a European solution to the “refugee crisis”, as noted in politicians' speeches (GR9-2018-Tsipras-CELEF). Centre-left media narratives on political speeches also included a rhetoric about the “European acquis, which means common values, human rights for all and not just for the natives, growth for more and more and the non-integration of fear” (GR10-2018-Vitsas-CELEF). The division and polarisation between anti-Europeans and pro-Europeans, which is cultivated by the conservative media, in the case of the centre-left media is transformed into a

Left-Right distinction (GR4-2016-Syriza Party-CELEF). In contrast with the conservative media reproducing politicians' discourses, the centre-left media criticize the distinction made between refugees, and "illegal immigrants" by mentioning that "even the dead (refugees) are 'illegal' for Dendias" (GR2-2013-Dendias-CELEF). Furthermore, the centre-left media reproduced centre-left politicians' discourses criticizing the "nationalisation" of border security policies as implemented by specific EU member states as well as the fact that "border protection" should not be the only issue deriving from refugee and migration management (GR10-2018-Vitsas-CELEF). Last but not least, as mentioned before, the centre-left media too reproduce the need for burden and responsibility-sharing between EU member states, and insist on the need for "solidarity" between EU member states.

6. Responses of Project Stakeholders

The role of the EU and the ways in which it has managed the so-called “refugee crisis” has been extensively commented upon by the project’s stakeholders in our interviews. The EU is considered to have adopted a **militaristic approach** towards immigration, according to a social worker, employee of an INGO in Lesvos. In this context, the member state governments played a crucial role, even in cases where their discourses were not explicitly anti-migrant. Furthermore, the deepening of capital accumulation and the increased austerity measures have led to a heightened ideological competition for the hegemony of the more conservative governments, according to the same social worker employed by the INGO in Lesvos. The **externalisation of migration**, as regards the current and future trends and aims of the EU on migration, was also mentioned in relation to the current revision of the EU-Turkey Statement and the agreements between Italy and Libya, as a legal counsellor in a local NGO in Lesvos mentioned.

The EU will continuously ratify agreements with countries to regulate migration. Therefore, migration routes to Europe will be so severely restricted that irregular entries will be surely criminalized. At the same time, irregular entry will more severely endanger the lives of those in search of protection (Legal counsellor in a local NGO in Lesvos).

The need for **burden-sharing** among EU member states as a widespread politicians’ narrative was also commented by the project’s stakeholders as well as **criticism on the Dublin Regulation**. The call for burden-sharing in issues of migration towards the EU is linked to the lack of a common EU migration policy, as a legal counsellor in the Asylum Committees commented. According to a social worker employed by an International Organisation in Lesvos, the narratives on burden-sharing are considered to reinforce the perception of migrants as a burden. The Dublin Regulation, according to which asylum seekers are forced to apply for asylum in the first country of entry, is considered to show a **lack of solidarity** between EU member states, leading to the failure of the EU project, according to a legal counsellor of an NGO in Lesvos. The issue of solidarity emerges from the perceptions of the RESPOND stakeholders as follows:

I believe that EU member states, and not only them, should have showed solidarity with Southern European countries. Certainly, this does not excuse the way Southern European states have dealt and are dealing with migration. This could have prevented the rise of far-right governments (Legal counsellor in a local NGO in Lesvos).

The lack of such solidarity and the decisions currently made by the EU have affected the attitude of local communities, especially those of the East Aegean islands where hotspots are established. According to the same stakeholder, strong negative feelings have emerged in these communities mostly against the EU, rather than against the national government. This hostility against EU policies also grows as a result of the extensive funding of humanitarian aid for migration purposes, while the Greeks had been left to fend for themselves during the financial crisis.

Furthermore, the use of the word “solidarity” by Greek state authorities in their call towards other member states is considered a trivialization of the term. According to an employee of an NGO in Lesvos, the current use of the term in politicians’ speeches has geopolitical dimensions and economic goals.

To reduce the rooting of anti-immigrant phobia in society, whatever the dimensions of this phobia are, a public discourse that analyses the phenomenon of immigration without

stereotypes and nationalist clichés is needed. We need a narrative that does not link immigration to national security issues. I generally believe that solidarity cannot come from phobic attitudes, but the above politicians' speeches include phobia. Charity may start from phobic attitudes, as can humanity in some ways, but not solidarity" (Employee in an NGO in Lesbos).

As regards the narratives on "Europeanisation" and the "nationalisation" of border security policies, the contradiction between the autonomy of the nation state and EU governmentality was commented as below. One issue that emerges is the increased funding of Frontex and the deployment of Frontex troops to non-EU member states bordering EU member states.

Frontex is currently being deployed at all EU external borders. The possibility of nationalizing external borders is non-existent at this moment. The current Greek government is welcoming Frontex operations at its borders, as the previous government did when it welcomed Frontex operations on the hotspots for registration purposes, and EASO to conduct the interviews with asylum applicants (Legal counsellor in a NGO in Lesbos).

Yet, the politicians' speeches are considered to reflect the ongoing debate regarding the strengthening of national policies in relation to EU policies, as a lawyer and a legal counsellor in the Asylum Committees commented. In this regard, the European Pact on Immigration and Asylum of 2008 was mentioned by the project's stakeholders as an example of potentially conflicting interests between EU member states.

One Member State's actions may affect the interests of the others. Access to the territory of one Member State may be followed by access to the others. It is consequently imperative that each Member State takes account of its partners' interests when designing and implementing its immigration, integration and asylum policies (Council of the European Union, 2008, p. 3).

According to an employee in an NGO in Lesbos, these statements push even more for the **militarisation of migration** and not for a social management thereof. This includes the externalisation of borders, the financial and administrative empowerment of Frontex, and large amount of money spent on border guards. A common European migration policy is not considered easily attainable, even more so considering the rise of far-right governments in different EU member states.

As regards the ways in which the aforementioned ideas and claims on the politicisation of Europe and the borders affect the role of the project's stakeholders in the field and at the local level, an employee in an NGO in Lesbos mentioned:

These are all pieces of a broader dynamic that fosters the understanding of immigration as a national security problem. In this context, the fields of reception, protection and integration become more of an issue of biopolitical practice and bureaucratic plot rather than of people management. Working in such a Kafkaesque setting, one soon realizes that one is hovering in a strange plot in which any move is pointless. After a number of frustrations, we now end up working in such a sensitive field just to survive, even if we started out with the awareness that immigration and refugee issues require (Employee of an NGO in Lesbos).

Conclusions

This report is part of the sixth work package of RESPOND and has focused on the question of Europeanisation. It discussed the developments in the party-political structure, the media structure, the events impacting on asylum/migration discourse since 2011, selected politicians' speeches during the investigated period, the circulation of narratives of the above speeches in the mainstream media, and the relevant responses of RESPOND's stakeholders.

In Greece, the financial crisis, the so-called "refugee crisis", the overall migration phenomenon, and the impact of all the aforementioned emerge as the catalysts for an important shift in discourses, politicising issues of Europeanisation. The role of the majority of the media in Greece during the investigated period was – explicitly or implicitly – to reproduce the different "crises" that characterized the circumstances in Greece. The ways in which this construction took place varied according to the political stance of the respective media, yet significant similarities can be observed that form certain large separating narratives. As regards the financial crisis and its implications, most narratives of mainstream politicians and the media repeatedly constructed the dilemma of anti-Europe versus pro-Europe, positioning themselves in the latter, and accompanied it with the spreading of fear of "Grexit". With respect to the refugee "crisis", most narratives of mainstream politicians and the media included – among others – the securitization of migration, the need for burden and responsibility-sharing and "solidarity" among EU member states, and narratives on the "Europeanisation" and "nationalisation" of border security policies. Common narratives throughout politicians and media of different political orientations insisted on a common criticism of Europe's lack of solidarity and the need for burden-sharing in the case of countries of first reception.

Furthermore, counter-discourses of solidarity with refugees emerged from the part of significant social movements, following the large social movements that unfolded during the financial crisis, yet existed in parallel with increased racism and racist violence. Following the 2019 electoral win of the conservative right-wing New Democracy, racism has been constantly on the rise, finding a fertile ground in specific settings. The cultivation of racism against "the foreigners" and migrants has been a systemic and institutional tool, used particularly since the emergence of the financial crisis in Greece to determine "the enemies" responsible for the country's sociopolitical situation.

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Appendices

Table 1: Table of Politicians' Speeches and Media Articles analysed

	CODING-Politician's speech	Politician	Role	Type of speech	Reference of speech	Media articles on politicians' speeches		
						Political group of media	CODING	Reference of media article
1	(GR1-2012-Papoutsis)	Christos Papoutsis	Minister of Citizen Protection, PASOK	Statement on the occasion of today's statements by the European Commission's representative, Michele Cercone, on the fence in Evros.	https://bit.ly/2BjwUsa	Conservative	(GR1-2012-Papoutsis-CONS)	https://bit.ly/2Voppa8
						Liberal	(GR1-2012-Papoutsis-LIB)	https://bit.ly/31qmGRf
						Centre-Left	(GR1-2012-Papoutsis-CELEF)	https://bit.ly/2BPHreo
2	(GR2-2013-Dendias)	Nikos Dendias	Minister of Public Order and Citizen Protection, ND	Reply to the question of Maria Giannakaki, Member of Parliament (DHMAR, centre-left party) concerning migration issue during the Greek Presidency of the EU.	https://bit.ly/3dGhVWj	Conservative	(GR2-2013-Dendias-CONS)	https://bit.ly/31uDcjh
						Liberal	(GR2-2013-Dendias-LIB)	https://bit.ly/2AaA68O
						Centre-Left	(GR2-2013-Dendias-CELEF)	https://bit.ly/2NFtGSc
3	(GR3-2014-Meimerakis)	Vaggelis Meimerakis	Chairperson of the Greek Parliament, ND	Speech in the Chairpersons' Conference of Parliamentary Committees for Union Affairs of the Parliaments of the EU (Chairpersons' COSAC) at Vilnius, Lithuania.	https://bit.ly/31oLXv8	Conservative	(GR3-2014-Meimerakis-CONS)	https://bit.ly/2AbM2qU
						Liberal		
						Centre-Left		
4	(GR4-2016-Syriza Party)	Central Committee of Syriza Party	Central Committee of Syriza Party, SYRIZA	Decision of the Central Committee of SYRIZA party regarding the refugees	https://bit.ly/3g5v50H	Conservative		
						Liberal	(GR4-2016-Syriza Party-LIB)	https://bit.ly/2BjJrAB
						Centre-Left	(GR4-2016-Syriza Party-CELEF)	https://bit.ly/2YGlg3f
5	(GR5-2016-Kotzias)	Nikos Kotzias	Minister for Foreign Affairs, SYRIZA	Statement for the Day of Europe, 9 May.	https://bit.ly/3gaBffQ	Conservative		
						Liberal	(GR5-2016-Kotzias-LIB)	https://bit.ly/31IOPZU
						Centre-Left	(GR5-2016-Kotzias-CELEF)	https://bit.ly/31uDzKH
6	(GR6-2017-Kaminis)	Giorgos Kaminis	Mayor of Athens, PASOK	Speech at the Mayors' meeting, held by the Committee of the	https://bit.ly/2BPAR7E	Conservative		
						Liberal	(GR6-2017-Kaminis-LIB)	https://bit.ly/2BcFjOa

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				Regions and the EUROCITIES network.		Centre-Left	(GR6-2017-Kaminis-CELEF)	https://bit.ly/2YLy1tL
7	(GR7-2017-Toskas)	Nikos Toskas	Deputy minister of citizen protection, SYRIZA	Speech entitled "The management of Migration Flows and the security and Solidarity Challenges for the EU" during the conference: "Europe's Limits: Security, Immigration, Human Rights", Institute of Democracy, Konstantinos Karamanlis, the Hanns-Seidel Foundation and Südosteuropa-Gesellschaft.	https://bit.ly/3g5YuYE	Conservative		
						Liberal	(GR7-2017-Toskas-LIB)	https://bit.ly/31pGwfv
						Centre-Left		
8	(GR8-2017-Samaras)	Antonis Samaras	Leader of New Democracy, ND	Speech at the European Ideas Network Conference, think tank of the European People's Party	https://bit.ly/38cKEAM	Conservative	(GR8-2017-Samaras-CONS)	https://bit.ly/2BLKNz9
						Liberal	(GR8-2017-Samaras-LIB)	https://bit.ly/3g75tjX
						Centre-Left		
9	(GR9-2018-Tsipras)	Alexis Tsipras	Prime Minister, SYRIZA	Statements after an informal EU leaders' mini-summit on asylum and migration, in Brussels	https://bit.ly/3dHdvhS	Conservative	(GR9-2018-Tsipras-CONS)	https://bit.ly/2Vth9FN
						Liberal	(GR9-2018-Tsipras-LIB)	https://bit.ly/2YE8PoO
						Centre-Left	(GR9-2018-Tsipras-CELEF)	https://bit.ly/31rol3y
10	(GR10-2018-Vitsas)	Dimitris Vitsas & Ioannis Balafas	Minister of Migration Policy and Deputy Minister of Migration Policy, SYRIZA	Press Conference	https://bit.ly/2NCrjib	Conservative	(GR10-2018-Vitsas-CONS)	https://bit.ly/2NEsWwJ
						Liberal	(GR10-2018-Vitsas-LIB)	https://bit.ly/2NQhTAV
						Centre-Left	(GR10-2018-Vitsas-CELEF)	https://bit.ly/2Zd49Fu